

Animated Musical Picture Clocks were very popular in the 19th century

Picture clocks were very popular in France, Germany, Austria, and Switzerland in the 19th century. Today, they are traded as sought-after collector's items at auctions. The paintings, which always contain a clock, often depict romantic landscapes. Some also have a striking mechanism or a music playing mechanism. The clockwork, the striking mechanism and the cylinder musical box are wound up with a key. Particularly astonishing are sophisticated picture clocks, in which people and things move automatically on the surface of the painting. They are reminiscent of automaton figures.

By Herbert Bruderer

As the name suggests, a working clock is embedded in a painting. The enamel dial is usually located in a church tower, occasionally a wall clock is present. The movement has a pendulum suspended by thread or spring. The pictures usually depict landscapes, lakes, rivers, mountains, cities, bridges, buildings (e.g. castles, cathedrals, windmills), workshops, sailing ships, carriages, railways or scenes with people and animals. The pictures are painted in oil on canvas, wood or sheet metal (e.g. iron, copper). The frame with the painting can be opened up so that the clockwork, striking mechanism and music playing mechanism are accessible. The multi-day clock movement is spring-driven. The musical mechanism has several airs. The bell strikes every quarter of an hour, half an hour or hour. Sometimes the paintings have an additional Angelus chime for the Angelus ringing. In the 19th century, especially in the Biedermeier period (first half of the 19th century), these mechanical paintings were widespread in Central Europe. Today, they can only be found in a few collections. In German, picture clocks are called "Bilderuhr". In French-speaking countries, the technical term is "tableau horloge" or "tableau à surprise".

Program controlled paintings with clockwork, musical mechanisms and moving objects are particularly fascinating. In certain complex picture clocks, parts of the painting move, such as people, animals, vehicles (e.g. cable cars, ships, carriages), and windmills. Flowing water is simulated by rotating glass rods. The creators of the picture clocks (clockmakers, painters) are often unknown. There were animated mechanical pictures as early as the 18th century, but they did not have a built-in clock (in French "tableau animé", "tableau mouvant", "tableau à mouvement et à musique", "tableau mécanique").

The following images (see Figures 1 to 6) come from Austria, France, Germany, the Netherlands, and Switzerland.

Fig. 1: Clock picture – picture clock. Coffee party on the Alster with a view over the Lombardsbrücke to the city of Hamburg, 1830. The work is one of the most remarkable objects in the collection of the Museum für Hamburgische Geschichte: the Hamburg picture clock with a movable panorama. The depiction of a family scene in front of the Alster with a view of the city is at first only a beautiful Biedermeier painting. However, when a complex mechanism is triggered, the picture starts to move and begins to sound: the figures move to the music, the mill turns, boats sail on the Außenalster and horsemen, soldiers and pedestrians walk across the Lombardsbrücke. Three clockworks move clocks, people playing ball or fishing, carts and carriages on the Lombardsbrücke. A music box makes several tunes sound. Credit: Stiftung Historische Museen Hamburg

Fig. 2: Picture clock „Tiroler Freiheitskämpfer“ (Tyrolean Freedom Fighters), Austria, Gustav Reibicek, oil painting on metal, spring-driven clock, automatic striking mechanism and comb-playing mechanism with three airs, around 1820. Credit: Wien Museum, Vienna, photo: Birgit and Peter Kainz, CC BY 4.0, U 136

Fig. 3: Musical picture clock with farrier's automaton, cylinder musical box, by Xavier Tharin, Paris, around 1860. When one of the three airs is played, the farrier on the left shoes the horse, the dog wags his tail, the two blacksmiths on the right strike the anvil, and the servant pulls on the rope of the bellows. Credit: Museum Speelklok, Utrecht, Netherlands, photo: Albertine Dijkema, www.museumspeelklok.nl, 0077

Fig. 4: Picture clock, Kramgasse Bern, probably Vienna or Munich, around 1830. Brass mechanism with fixed barrels, verge escapement, short rear pendulum, half-hour and hour striking mechanism. Bequest Rosa Kellenberger-Zürcher. Credit: Uhrenmuseum Museum Winterthur, Switzerland, photo: Michael Lio, Inv. 350

Fig. 5: Picture clock with music box. The painter of this picture clock is unknown. The movement is by Vincenti & Cie, Montbéliard. A Swiss music box from the beginning of the 19th century is coupled with the clock. Credit: Musée de l'horlogerie de Saint-Nicolas d'Alérimont, France, inv. 206.17.02

Fig. 6: Animated musical picture clock with river, bridge and windmill, from the period 1800–1825. Credit: Musée des arts et métiers-Cnam, Paris, Foto: Pascal Faligot, inv 20357

Acknowledgments

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Further reading

This article is based on the following work.

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 3. Auflage 2020

Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer, 3rd edition 2020

Bruderer, Herbert: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 3rd edition 2020, volume 1, 970 pages, 577 figures, 114 tables,

<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110669664>

Bruderer, Herbert: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 3rd edition 2020, volume 2, 1055 pages, 138 figures, 37 tables,

<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110669671>

Bruderer, Herbert: Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer Nature Switzerland AG, Cham, 3rd edition 2020, 2 volumes, 2113 pages, 715 illustrations, 151 tables, translated from the German by Dr John McMinn, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-40974-6>

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